

TRUMP'S POLICY ISSUES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6539044>

Otakhonov Komil

World Economy and Diplomacy

University Masters

Annotatsiya: Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlari 44-prezidenti bo'lmish Donald Trampning to'rt yillik prezidentlik davrida, AQSH tashqi siyosatida, ko'plab burilishlarga boy bo'ldi. Donald Tramp administratsiyasi asosiy e'tiborni iqtisodiy muammolarga qaratgan bo'lsada, ularning oldini olish va yechimini topish bilan shug'ullangan. Lekin, barchasi ham o'ylagandek bo'lavermaydi, chunki Tramp iqtisodiy tomondan ko'plab muammolarga uchraydi. Uning iqtisodiy muammolarga qarshi kurashishi katta savdo urushining boshlanishiga olib keladi va buning ortidan Trampning Amerika iqtisodiyotini ozmuncha qiyin ahvolga ham solib qo'yish holati ham kuzatiladi. Ushbu maqola aynan shu muammolar to'g'risida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Savdo urushi, NAFTA, Donald Trump, ishsizlik, "Phase One", texnologiya, tariflar, ishchi kuchi.

Abstract: During the four years of the presidency of Donald Trump, the 44th President of the United States, US foreign policy has been rich in many twists and turns. Although the Donald Trump administration has focused on economic problems and is working to prevent them and find solutions. But not everything is as it seems, because Trump has a lot of economic problems. His fight against economic problems will lead to the unleashing of a major trade war that will put Trump's US economy in a less dire situation. This article addresses these issues.

Keywords. Trade war, NAFTA, Donald Trump, job shortage, "Phase One", technology, tariffs, labor.

Аннотация: За четыре года президентства Дональда Трампа, 44-го президента США, внешняя политика США была богата на множество поворотов. Хотя администрация Дональда Трампа сосредоточилась на экономических проблемах и работает над их предотвращением и поиском решений. Но не все так, как кажется, потому что у Трампа много экономических проблем. Его борьба с экономическими проблемами приведет к развязыванию крупной торговой войны, которая поставит экономику США Трампа в менее тяжелое положение. В данной статье рассматриваются эти вопросы.

Ключевые слова. Торговая война, НАФТА, Дональд Трамп, нехватка рабочих мест, "Phase One", технологии, тарифы, рабочая сила.

During Donald Trump's initial term as president, he derailed deals by starting a trade war with China. His mission ensures that the conflict was triumphant and that his strategies were getting back manufacturing jobs that are active on abroad- until the pandemic hit, so the voters should give him an extra four years.

His political opponents were disagree.

"You lost that trade war," snapped Sen. Kamala Harris during a discussion with Vice President Mike Pence, referring to the 300,000 manufacturing job shortage during the Trump administration and bankrupt farmers.³⁶

As a market analysis demonstrated that studying global monetary mechanisms, Trump's motivation to rethink his monetary strategy was reasonable. Assuming that deregulation has harmed American workers, it makes sense that creating barriers to exchange—a willingness to "get into the battle" anyway—might protect these professionals. In any case, wars can misfire - and trade wars are the same.

More sufferings then benefits

The trade war has caused monetary pain on both sides and led to the redirection of exchange flows from both China and the US. As Heather Long described in The Washington Post: "USA monetary development slowed, business stalled and businesses began to hire fewer people."³⁷

The monetary hypothesis³⁸ allows us to understand that deregulation implies a more remarkable availability of less expensive products, since everything will be delivered to where it can be manufactured at the lowest cost.

This sounds like an incredible agreement for customers and merchants like farms that keep track of more consumers for their wares. However, it is a terrible scheme to gather employers as processing plants move to countries like China or Mexico where labor costs are lower.

In 2016, Donald Trump began presidential campaign and resistance to economic agreements like NAFTA was one of his unique challenges.³⁹ Whenever

³⁶ Kamala Harris. *Highlights of the VP Debate*. October 8, 2020

<https://www.factcheck.org/2020/10/video-highlights-of-the-vp-debate/>

³⁷ Heather Long. *Was Trump's China trade war worth it?* January 15, 2020.

<https://www.washingtonpost.com/business/2020/01/15/was-trumps-china-trade-war-worth-it/>

³⁸ WTO. *Trade and employment*. 2007

https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/---publ/documents/publication/wcms_091038.pdf

³⁹ Donald Trump. *Donald Trump's speech*. June 28, 2018

Republican politicians tended to free exchange, his guarantee of the return of production to the United States assisted him to gain the main thing - and eventually the presidency - as a rising quantum of voters began to consider the commerce terrible for US citizens.⁴⁰

What's more, Donald Trump followed through on his promise to impose mandatory tariffs on a number of Chinese goods - that were valued at \$550 billion⁴¹ as well as on most on steel and aluminum imports. Subsequently, Trump's versus Chinese trade war began.

Most research analysis shows that, the economic deals have undeniably harm the majority of U.S. business holders. However, Trump's trade war did not handle the offshoring issue they were supposed to solve.

The trade war issues

Trump said, "Trade war are good and easy to win"⁴² because Americans are the consumers (China - traders).

Trump seems to have articulated this on the assumption that America's accomplice swapping would not fight back but he was wrong.

Over many talks, China has repeatedly fought back by taxing US\$185 billion⁴³, mostly spent on agricultural goods. After American soy farmers saw their biggest market evaporate, the Trump organization had to spend \$23 billion to make up for some of its setbacks.⁴⁴ Overall, in 2020, more than 33%⁴⁵ of the farmer's wages came from government as a sponsorship.

This was the problem of the trade war that, American government and business owners faced. They expected to shield the country's own workers, but end up hurting themselves a lot as retaliatory tariffs drive up the cost of goods, hurting some companies and workers both inland and abroad.

<https://time.com/4386335/donald-trump-trade-speech-transcript/>

⁴⁰ **Republicans.** *Republicans, especially Trump supporters, see free trade deals as bad for U.S.* March 31, 2016

<https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2016/03/31/>

⁴¹ **China Briefing.** *The US-China Trade War: A Timeline.* August 25, 2020.

<https://www.china-briefing.com/news/the-us-china-trade-war-a-timeline/>

⁴² **Donald Trump on Twitter.** 2016

<https://twitter.com/realDonaldTrump/status/969525362580484098>

⁴³ **Wendong Zhang, Minghao Li.** *Most US farmers remain loyal to Trump despite pain from trade war and COVID-19.*

October 19, 2020. <https://theconversation.com/most-us-farmers-remain-loyal-to-trump-despite-pain-from-trade-wars-and-covid-19-146535>

⁴⁴ **Lowa State University.** *The State-level Burden of the Trade War: Interactions between the Market Facilitation Program and Tariffs.*

https://www.card.iastate.edu/ag_policy_review/article/?a=103

⁴⁵ **Mark Weinraub.** *Trump's payments to farmers hit all-time high ahead of election.* October 19, 2020

<https://www.reuters.com/article/usa-election-farmers-aid/trumps-payments-to-farmers-hit-all-time-high-ahead-of-election-idUKL1N2GT1C8>

At the same time, the US strategy does not appear to have focused on the first adversary: the offshoring of US positions, which continued to evolve. The tax cuts in 2017⁴⁶, for instance, did make offshoring more profitable and attractive, making it much more difficult to achieve the main aim of a trade war.

In 2020, the United States and China reached a visible and enforceable agreement on the Phase One Economic Agreement, which requires initial changes and various changes to China's foreign exchange system in the areas of licensed innovation, technology transfer, agriculture and cash management. The Phase 1 agreement also includes China's responsibility for acquiring significant additional US labor and products in the near future.

While this may offset some of the harm caused by the trade war, such as helping to soy ranchers, it could make offshoring easier by making it more profitable and productive to move US businesses to China. This is because China also had a deal to stop demanding foreign companies that try to continue working within its lines to move innovation to their homegrown accomplices.

China has also felt financial difficulties because of a trade war, but apparently not enough to succumb to the Trump Administration's central demands for major primary changes. To be sure, as the trade war dragged on, Beijing cut its tariffs on its other exchange partners as it reduced its dependence on US markets. The latest agreement, which the parties announced on January 15, 2020, is in many ways similar to the proposal that Beijing has been putting forward since the beginning: increased purchases of goods in addition to commitments to better licensing, innovation, money, and limited innovation.

The agreement lacked any positive progress on the allocations, government efforts, and goals of China's modern approach to advantage its own organizations over unfamiliar rivals. Progress in market access is also disappointing outside the monetary area.

If we analyze the economic influence of the both country, we can see that China is overweighting in almost all regions by its economic potentiality. In addition, U.S. today feels more threat to its hegemon policy in economic position also, which U.S. has already lost from this some regions. For that reason, there are huge amount of issues on foreign policy of United States of America mostly towards Asia. Most rivalry of United States and People's Republic of China we have faced in administration of Donald Trump, where there had been colossal trade war, technological competition through 5G technology or Artificial Intelligence, we saw

⁴⁶ **Jane C. Timm.** *Trump signs tax cut bill, first big legislative win.* December 27, 2017
<https://www.nbcnews.com/politics/politics-news/trump-signs-tax-cut-bill-first-big-legislative-win-n832141>

sanction diplomacy that we saw during the administration of Trump, collisions in China Sea where U.S. navy floats and harbors are located. Summing up all this views, we can say US authority is not in a good position where they are losing their unipolar hegemony in all sectors, as we see ongoing crisis in Europe (Ukraine), where Russia shows its muscles to Western nations and PRC is supporting his old brother country, countering to Western hegemony. Moreover, we can say this ongoing conflict, the inception part of Cold War 2.0⁴⁷, as a great deal of experts conclude their opinions the same.

LIST OF LITERATURE

1. **Kamala Harris.** *Highlights of the VP Debate.* October 8, 2020
<https://www.factcheck.org/2020/10/video-highlights-of-the-vp-debate/>
2. **Heather Long.** *Was Trump's China trade war worth it?* January 15, 2020.
<https://www.washingtonpost.com/business/2020/01/15/was-trumps-china-trade-war-worth-it/>
3. **WTO.** *Trade and employment.* 2007
https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/---publ/documents/publication/wcms_091038.pdf
4. **Donald Trump.** *Donald Trump's speech.* June 28, 2018
<https://time.com/4386335/donald-trump-trade-speech-transcript/>
5. **Republicans.** *Republicans, especially Trump supporters, see free trade deals as bad for U.S.* March 31, 2016
<https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2016/03/31/>
6. **China Briefing.** *The US-China Trade War: A Timeline.* August 25, 2020.
<https://www.china-briefing.com/news/the-us-china-trade-war-a-timeline/>
7. **Donald Trump on Twitter.** 2016
<https://twitter.com/realDonaldTrump/status/969525362580484098>
8. **Wendong Zhang, Minghao Li.** *Most Us farmers remain loyal to Trump despite pain from trade war and COVID-19.* October 19, 2020.
<https://theconversation.com/most-us-farmers-remain-loyal-to-trump-despite-pain-from-trade-wars-and-covid-19-146535>

⁴⁷ **Latimes.com.** *Column: Welcome to Cold War 2.0. It won't be easy.* February 26, 2022
<https://www.latimes.com/politics/story/2022-02-26/welcome-to-cold-war-2-0-it-wont-be-easy>

9. **Lowa State University.** *The State-level Burden of the Trade War: Interactions between the Market Facilitation Program and Tariffs.*
https://www.card.iastate.edu/ag_policy_review/article/?a=103
10. **Mark Weinraub.** *Trump's payments to farmers hit all-time high ahead of election.* October 19, 2020
<https://www.reuters.com/article/usa-election-farmers-aid/trumps-payments-to-farmers-hit-all-time-high-ahead-of-election-idUKL1N2GT1C8>
11. **Jane C. Timm.** *Trump signs tax cut bill, first big legislative win.* December 27, 2017
<https://www.nbcnews.com/politics/politics-news/trump-signs-tax-cut-bill-first-big-legislative-win-n832141>
12. **Latimes.com.** *Column: Welcome to Cold War 2.0. It won't be easy.* February 26, 2022
<https://www.latimes.com/politics/story/2022-02-26/welcome-to-cold-war-2-0-it-wont-be-easy>

